

Question raised by requestor

What constitutes the minimum standard for social contact for horses kept in captivity?

What constitutes the minimum standard for (free) movement for horses kept in captivity?

Answer

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* received the question on 6 January 2025 and the response was sent on 9 January 2025 to the requestor. Since EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* already published information on this topic, the answer to the question can be found in Lansade et al. (2024) Review – Confinement, restriction of social contacts and movement in domestic horses. The review is published on the Website of EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines*: https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/knowledge_base/confinement-and-restriction-of-movement-and-social-contact-in-horses/

Reference

Lansade, L., Hartmann, E., Minero, M., & Ruet, A. (2024). Review – Confinement, restriction of social contacts and movement in domestic horses. EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785436>

Designated by
the EU Commission

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* provides a 'Questions to EURCAW' (Q2E) service for official inspectors and policy workers. Please, send us an email with your question at info@eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu